

Operational Readiness Assessment of a Magnetically-Adhered Crawler for Oil Spill Emergency Hull Sealing under Offshore Conditions

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Abstract

Oil spills from ship hull breaches pose critical risks to marine ecosystems, especially during the early response window. This study presents a magnetically adhered crawler system capable of sealing hull breaches under offshore conditions without diver intervention. The system combines magnetic track mobility, mechanical anchor deployment, and a winch-driven sealing pad into a modular platform suitable for rapid aerial or vessel transport.

Developed with guidance from the Korea Coast Guard, the platform was validated through full-scale trials conducted both on land and at sea. Offshore tests were performed under real-sea conditions involving wave-induced motion, reduced visibility, and equipment handling challenges. Despite these constraints, the crawler demonstrated stable locomotion, secure anchor engagement, and reliable sealing performance under hydrostatic pressures up to 75 kPa.

Key operational issues included tether management and magnetic interference during helicopter transport. Nevertheless, the system consistently achieved effective sealing in dynamic marine environments. These findings support its readiness for offshore deployment and highlight its potential to enhance early-stage containment while minimizing personnel risk. The crawler offers a practical, field-tested solution for integration into national oil spill emergency response frameworks.

Keywords: oil spill, hull breach, magnetic crawler, offshore sealing system, emergency response

1. Introduction

Marine oil spills resulting from ship collisions or hull failures remain among the most serious environmental threats in maritime domains. Such events not only pollute ocean ecosystems but

also cause prolonged economic and social disruption in coastal communities. A representative case is the 2007 Hebei Spirit oil spill off the coast of Taean, South Korea, which released over 10,800 tons of crude oil into the sea following a hull breach. The incident severely damaged local fisheries, tourism, and ecosystems, requiring years of recovery efforts.

Various containment technologies—such as floating booms, skimmers, and chemical dispersants—have been deployed in past incidents. However, their effectiveness in open-sea conditions is often limited. Environmental factors like wave action, currents, and wind commonly interfere with deployment, especially in the early hours of an incident when containment is most critical. Studies show that mechanical containment success drops significantly if not initiated within the first 6 hours of the spill (Hong, 2020).

A more direct and efficient approach is to seal the hull breach at its source before large-scale leakage occurs. Traditional methods involve diver-assisted techniques such as plugging or welding, which are dangerous and technically challenging under offshore conditions. Recent developments include magnet-attached sealing pads and inflatable plugs, but these still rely on manual placement and often lack the sealing strength needed for high-discharge scenarios or complex hull geometries.

In response to this challenge, and based on a technical request from the Korea Coast Guard, a remotely operated hull sealing system was developed. The system is based on a magnetically adhered crawler platform designed to traverse steel hull surfaces, locate breaches, and deploy a mechanical anchor and sealing pad capable of withstanding offshore conditions and hydrostatic discharge pressures.

This paper presents the system architecture, its mechanical and operational modules, and the results of full-scale field tests conducted under both land-based and offshore scenarios. The findings demonstrate the system's readiness for deployment and its potential to improve early-stage oil spill containment without diver intervention.

2. Related Work and Technical Gaps

Previous approaches to sealing hull breaches during marine-spill incidents have primarily relied on diver-assisted interventions such as hammering wooden plugs or welding steel plates directly onto the hull. These methods are highly labour-intensive, dangerous, and largely ineffective under real offshore conditions, where waves, currents, and limited visibility make precise underwater work difficult or impossible. Moreover, the risk of structural collapse or further leakage during manual operations is non-negligible—particularly in the early stages of an oil spill, when containment speed is critical.

To overcome these limitations, a range of semi-mechanised sealing devices has been developed both internationally and domestically. Representative approaches include magnetically adhered pads, inflatable sealing bags, suction-type sealing blankets, and mechanically actuated plugs. Although these solutions reduce direct human intervention and accelerate deployment, they remain constrained by three persistent issues: (1) insufficient adhesion strength under high discharge pressure (typically above 50–75 kPa); (2) limited adaptability to curved or corroded steel surfaces; and (3) operational unreliability in turbulent offshore environments.

Among commercially available technologies, the Magnetic Plaster developed by MIKO Marine (Norway) is one of the most widely recognized. The system comprises a flexible magnetic patch that can be manually attached to the external hull surface to seal minor breaches (see Figure 1). It is effective for low-pressure leaks on flat or gently curved hulls in calm waters. However, it lacks the magnetic adhesion force required to withstand high flow rates or dynamic hull motion, restricting its applicability in offshore spill scenarios (Miko Marine AS, 2024).

Figure 1. MIKO Marine's magnetic plaster for hull breach sealing. A magnet-based patch designed to seal minor breaches under low-pressure and flat-surface conditions. Source: MIKO Marine AS (<https://mikomarine.com>)

In South Korea, several prototypes have emerged from public-sector research initiatives, including magnetically attached inflatable mats, butterfly-valve sealing units, and pneumatically actuated closure systems. While promising in controlled laboratory tests, these devices face practical constraints: valve-type units often exceed 15 kg and require cranes or chain blocks for handling; inflatable solutions cannot maintain sealing above 50 kPa; and all existing systems still depend on divers or operators for precise hull positioning, limiting usefulness during the crucial early-response window (Moon et al., 2013).

International patents from organizations such as Lockheed Martin and ConocoPhillips describe more sophisticated sealing mechanisms that employ internal anchoring or mechanically actuated

clamps. Yet these designs generally assume stable operating environments and necessitate preparatory work, such as surface cleaning or mechanical fixation, and their effectiveness under realistic offshore accident conditions remains largely unverified (Lockheed Martin Corp., 2013; ConocoPhillips Co., 2008).

In summary, existing commercial products and research prototypes commonly fall short in at least one of three critical aspects: rapid deployability, resistance to discharge pressures above 75 kPa, and independence from direct human contact with the damaged hull. The 75 kPa benchmark corresponds to the hydrostatic pressure exerted by seawater on hull breaches located 7.5–10 m above sea level—representing a realistic upper bound for oil spill discharge from exposed sections of large tankers during vessel motion. These persistent limitations—spanning deployability, pressure resistance, and autonomy—constitute the core technical gaps that the present study aims to address through a new remotely operable sealing system.

3. System Description and Architecture

The developed sealing system is designed for remote intervention in offshore oil spill scenarios, where diver-free, rapid deployment is critical. The system is composed of four main components, each functionally represented in Figure 2: (1) a remote control unit, (2) a power supply console, (3) a crawler platform, and (4) a detachable sealing pad with a traction system.

The remote control unit enables wireless communication with the crawler. This unit offers essential mobility and sealing control functions, including locomotion commands, anchor arm actuation, and winch control. In addition to joystick-based manual input, the system supports simplified control through a compact wireless remote device—designed to ensure redundancy and flexibility during confined or mobile deployment conditions.

The power supply subsystem, housed in a ruggedized console, integrates a high-capacity lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery pack. It provides stabilized power to the crawler via a tether cable that also carries control signals. This console allows operation for over two hours without external power, supporting rapid deployment from vessels or temporary field bases without bulky generators. A video display embedded in the console allows real-time visual monitoring via the crawler's onboard camera.

The crawler, which serves as the primary field-operable unit, consists of two primary subsystems:

- A mobile body equipped with magnetic track mechanisms, enabling traversal on steel hulls regardless of surface inclination.

- An anchor deployment arm that inserts a mechanical anchoring element into a breach to establish a sealing point. The arm is actuated by compact geared motors and encoders, offering targeting capability with three degrees of freedom (DOF) for various breach geometries.

Once the crawler positions itself at the breach and deploys the anchor, it activates a sealing pad mounted at its base. This pad, connected by a steel cable, is tensioned against the hull surface using an internal winch. Once full tension is achieved, the crawler detaches, leaving the sealing pad in place to suppress further fluid discharge from the breach.

The system architecture prioritizes modularity, robustness, and ease of field deployment. All core components—crawler, console, battery pack, and sealing pad—are designed for transport via helicopter or vessel and allow rapid on-site assembly without the need for specialized tools. Key mechanical considerations included water ingress protection, saltwater corrosion resistance, and impact durability.

Figure 2. Integrated system overview of the crawler-based sealing platform. (Left) Schematic block diagram showing major subsystems, power and control signal flow, and operational relationships. (Right) 3D rendered model of the fully assembled crawler with labeled anchor deployment arm, magnetic tracks, and sealing pad, highlighting modular construction and field deployability.

4. System Design and Operational Modules

The crawler-based sealing platform was designed with a strong emphasis on field operability, environmental resilience, and modular subsystem integration. While Section 3 presented the architectural overview of the entire system, this section focuses on the operational role and physical design of each individual module that enables remote sealing operations.

Each module—including mobility tracks, anchoring mechanisms, sealing interfaces, and control/power systems—was engineered to withstand the dynamic challenges of offshore deployments. The design process prioritized portability, ease of field assembly, and operational reliability, ensuring that the system can function effectively without diver intervention.

Sections 4.1 through 4.5 describe each component’s functional contribution to the sealing process, with emphasis on mechanical behavior, deployment workflow, and field maintainability.

4.1 Magnetic Mobility Platform

The crawler’s magnetic mobility platform enables traversal on steel hulls regardless of orientation, including vertical or inverted configurations. This capability is essential for accessing submerged or elevated breach locations without diver assistance. The system was engineered to maintain stable traction on wet, inclined, and partially corroded surfaces typically encountered in offshore oil spill scenarios.

Figure 3 illustrates the operational sequence of the crawler-based sealing process. The crawler first magnetically adheres to the steel surface and moves toward the breach. Once in position, a mechanical anchor is inserted to establish a fixed point, followed by the deployment and tensioning of a sealing pad. The crawler then detaches, leaving the pad in place.

Figure 3. Sequential operation of the crawler-based sealing platform. (Left) Magnetic traversal to breach site; (Center) anchor insertion; (Right) sealing pad tensioning and crawler detachment.

To support the operations illustrated in Figure 3, a static mechanical model was developed to validate the platform's ability to adhere and climb on inclined steel surfaces, as shown in Figure 4. The equilibrium conditions are expressed in Equations (1) through (6), which served as design constraints during the selection of magnets, rubber friction pads, and drive motors.

Figure 4. Static force model for vertical climbing. Variables: F_m – magnetic adhesion force; F_f – frictional force; N_i – normal force at the i -th magnet; W – gravitational force (weight); μ – friction coefficient; ϕ – hull inclination angle; L_i – distance from contact point to i -th magnet; L_A – horizontal distance from front track to center of gravity; h_w – vertical height of weight above the hull; h_s – vertical distance to drive shaft.

$$F_f = 2\mu \sum_{i=1}^n N_i = \mu(2nF_m - W \sin \phi) \quad (1)$$

$$F_m = \frac{W}{2n} (\mu^{-1} \cos \phi + \sin \phi) \quad (2)$$

$$\sum M_A = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n (N_i - F_m)L_i + Wh_w \cos \phi + WL_A \sin \phi = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$F_m \geq \frac{W(h_w \cos \phi + L_A \sin \phi)}{2 \sum_{i=1}^n L_i} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum M_O = -2\tau + W(L_A \sin \phi + (h_w - h_s) \cos \phi) < 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\tau > \frac{1}{2}W(L_A \sin \phi + (h_w - h_s) \cos \phi) \quad (6)$$

Equations (1) and (2) define the total available friction and the required magnetic adhesion force, respectively, as functions of crawler weight and hull inclination. Equation (3) models moment balance about the front contact edge to prevent forward tipping, and Equation (4) provides a lower bound for magnetic force needed to maintain contact. Equations (5) and (6) relate to rearward stability: Equation (5) expresses moment balance to prevent peeling, while Equation (6) specifies the minimum motor torque required for uphill movement. These equations guided the selection of magnet count and strength, rubber pad geometry, and drive motor capacity, with a safety factor of 1.5 to 2.0 applied for offshore uncertainty.

To implement these theoretical requirements, each mobility module was designed using a stainless-steel chain with aluminum-based shoes. Each shoe contains a central neodymium magnet (N50, 50×20×10 mm) in a unidirectional Halbach array, enhancing magnetic flux on the hull-facing side while minimizing stray fields. Chevron-shaped urethane pads protrude slightly from the shoe surface, establishing rubber contact before magnetic engagement. These grooves aid in water drainage and increase shear resistance under wet conditions.

The magnet and rubber components are housed in a waterproof cover, as shown in Figure 5. A mechanical interlock secures each shoe to the track, preventing detachment under vibration. The modular design allows for individual shoe replacement in the field. Field tests confirmed that the magnetic mobility platform maintained stable traction on inclined and wet steel surfaces without slippage.

Figure 5. Magnetic shoe structure and configuration. (Left) Distribution of the magnetic field based on a Halbach array. (Center) Cross-sectional view showing the rubber pad and magnet module. (Right) Photograph of the fully assembled magnetic track module as mounted on the crawler for field deployment.

4.2 Anchor Deployment Unit

The anchor deployment unit enables mechanical engagement within a hull breach, serving as a structural fixture to which sealing force can be applied. The unit consists of a compact deployment mechanism mounted on the crawler and a U-shaped serrated anchor designed to remain securely seated once inserted into the breach.

To assist with insertion planning, a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation was conducted using a representative breach geometry. Figure 6 (left) illustrates the velocity and pressure distribution of oil outflow. Areas exhibiting strong outflow were selected as target insertion zones—not because they resist more, but because high fluid velocity typically indicates a clear internal passage. These regions are less likely to contain structural obstructions or debris, thereby increasing the probability of successful anchor engagement deep inside the breach.

The insertion sequence, outlined in the flowchart of Figure 6 (right), incorporates feedback from a contact-force sensor positioned at the interface between the anchor deployment unit and the crawler body. This sensor detects external force generated by fluid drag during probe movement, enabling the system to iteratively adjust the insertion orientation. Once the arm encounters the location of peak fluid resistance, presumed to be aligned with the clearest path into the breach, the anchor is deployed and tensioned via the onboard winch. This ensures that the anchor remains seated regardless of final insertion angle or direction.

Figure 6. CFD-based simulation of oil ejection and anchor insertion sequence. (Left) Velocity and pressure distributions at the breach, with arrows indicating outflow direction and magnitude. (Right) Stepwise anchor deployment logic based on maximizing drag force detection through directional alignment.

The anchor itself is a 600 mm-long U-shaped stainless-steel rod with serrated ends. The U-shaped cross-section was specifically chosen over solid or cylindrical forms to leverage flow-induced rotational alignment. During oil discharge, the anchor tends to passively rotate so that the bottom of the U faces into the breach, increasing the likelihood that the serrated edges contact the internal

wall. This behavior significantly enhances seating stability without requiring high-precision alignment during insertion.

The serrated tips are magnetized to assist with initial engagement, and the main anchor body is made from a stainless steel grade compatible with magnetic tip functionality. Strategically placed perforations along the arms reduce the anchor's overall weight while maintaining structural strength. These features collectively support robust engagement even under dynamic discharge conditions.

Structural strength was verified through finite element analysis, as shown in the left panel of Figure 7. The analysis confirmed that the anchor could withstand loads exceeding those generated by the crawler's sealing system, ensuring a sufficient safety margin under various operating conditions—even when insertion angles are suboptimal.

Land-based validation tests, illustrated in the right panel of Figure 7, were conducted using breach modules of varying geometries, including both circular and irregular shapes. In all cases, the anchor was successfully inserted and retained its position during continuous discharge, confirming its adaptability and effectiveness across different breach types.

The deployment mechanism is embedded within the crawler's body and features three degrees of freedom, enabling precise control over arm articulation. Combined with onboard visual feedback and real-time drag sensing, the system ensures robust anchor placement even in turbid or low-visibility underwater environments.

Figure 7. Anchor strength and deployment validation. (Left) Finite element analysis showing von Mises stress distribution under wire tension. (Right) Photographs of the anchor stably seated in circular (top) and irregular (bottom) breach modules during controlled discharge conditions.

4.3 Sealing Pad and Winch Mechanism

The sealing pad and winch mechanism are responsible for generating and maintaining contact pressure between the hull surface and the sealing interface, thereby suppressing further discharge from the breach after anchor deployment. Once the anchor is inserted and fixed, the sealing pad—mounted beneath the crawler—is pulled tightly against the breach opening using a wire wound by an onboard winch system.

The sealing pad is fabricated from a multi-layered elastomeric polymer with high compressibility and chemical resistance. Each layer is approximately 10 mm thick, and multiple layers are stacked to enhance the pad's ability to deform in response to irregular hull geometries. This layered structure enables conformal contact over uneven or corroded surfaces while maintaining consistent sealing pressure.

Figure 8 (right) shows the fabricated pad and a cross-sectional view of its stacked structure. To evaluate its mechanical behavior under compressive loading, finite element analysis was conducted using a simplified pad model. Figure 8 (left and center) presents the simulation results under various boundary conditions. The analysis confirmed that the compressive stress is evenly distributed across the contact surface, even when localized force is applied via the wire and anchor. The von Mises stress distribution remained within the material's elastic range at operational tension levels, indicating structural reliability under field conditions.

The pad is pulled into position by a stainless-steel cable connected to the anchor. A compact winch mechanism embedded in the crawler body applies the necessary retraction force. This winch is equipped with a torque limiter to prevent over-tensioning, which could damage the pad or dislodge the anchor. Once the pre-defined tension is reached, the winch automatically disengages, and the crawler detaches, leaving the pad firmly in place over the breach.

The sealing process is designed to remain effective under non-ideal hull conditions, including wet, inclined, or corroded surfaces. Field tests have demonstrated that the combination of compliant materials, controlled tension, and a flexible structural design enables the pad to maintain prolonged and stable contact during offshore deployment.

Figure 8. Structural analysis and fabricated sealing pad. (Left) Finite element simulation showing deformation under applied tensile load. (Right) Fabricated pad composed of a thin silicone sealing layer backed by lightweight polyethylene foam.

4.4 Control Interface and Power System

The crawler is operated via two control interfaces: a primary field console and a compact wireless controller. The console, housed in a rugged waterproof case, integrates the control interface and power supply system into a single unit. It features live video monitoring, dual joysticks, a keyboard, and control switches, allowing operators to manage crawler locomotion and sealing actions while viewing real-time footage from onboard cameras.

A high-capacity lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery is embedded within the console enclosure. This battery was selected for its high safety margin, thermal stability, and ability to deliver consistent voltage under variable load conditions. It provides sufficient energy to support at least two hours of continuous field operation. An internal DC-AC inverter regulates power delivery to subsystems and a communication module enables both tethered and wireless control. Power and signal are transmitted through a flexible tether cable that is secured with a safety line to facilitate organized handling during deployment.

To support field deployment in mobile or space-constrained environments, a lightweight wireless remote controller was also developed at the request of the Korean Coast Guard. This RF-based controller provides basic access to crawler functions—including locomotion, anchor deployment arm operation, and emergency stop—and is particularly intended for use near the damaged vessel, where the operator can directly monitor the crawler's position through either onboard camera feedback or visual line of sight. This configuration allows the operator to perform fine adjustments during critical tasks such as anchor alignment and sealing under more intuitive control conditions.

To prevent command conflicts, the crawler system is designed to automatically prioritize commands from the tethered console when both interfaces are active. This ensures operational safety and prevents unintended actions due to overlapping inputs.

This fully integrated dual-interface design minimizes setup time and improves deployment flexibility, enabling the crawler to be operated efficiently under varying field conditions, including offshore emergencies requiring rapid and localized intervention.

Figure 9. Control interfaces for the crawler sealing platform. (Left) The console provides control interfaces, video feedback, and a built-in lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery pack. (Right) The wireless remote controller enables simplified operation near the damaged vessel with direct visual monitoring.

4.5 Design Philosophy and Operational Considerations

The development of the crawler-based sealing system was driven by the need to respond quickly and safely to hull breaches in offshore environments. Such incidents often occur under adverse conditions, including high winds, low visibility, and unstable sea states. These factors, combined with the risk of hazardous material leakage, make direct human intervention extremely dangerous and often impractical. Traditionally, sealing tasks have relied on divers or manual patching operations, but these approaches are not viable when time is limited and weather conditions deteriorate rapidly.

Given these constraints, the Korea Coast Guard requested a system capable of being launched from a nearby response vessel without requiring human access to the damaged ship. To meet this need, the crawler was designed to balance operational effectiveness with simplicity and robustness, allowing it to be deployed in challenging environments and operated by remote personnel with minimal setup.

Rather than pursuing full autonomy, which would introduce complexity and potential failure modes under unpredictable field conditions, the system adopts a human-in-the-loop architecture.

All major functions—including crawler movement, anchor insertion, and sealing pad tensioning—are carried out under direct operator control. However, limited automation is introduced where it enhances reliability and safety. For example, the crawler is equipped with a drag sensor to help the operator identify the breach location even when the camera view is obscured. The winch system includes a torque-limiting clutch that disengages automatically when a predefined preload is reached, ensuring consistent sealing force without risk of over-tensioning.

The mechanical design prioritizes field transparency, modularity, and durability. The crawler's magnetic tracks, featuring Halbach-arranged neodymium magnets and rubberized pads, maintain adhesion on vertical or inverted hull surfaces, even when contaminated with oil or biofilm. The system is divided into transportable components—crawler body, control console, sealing pad—that can be quickly assembled on-site without specialized tools. All external housings meet water ingress protection standards, and structural components are made of corrosion-resistant materials suitable for marine environments.

The sealing pad is integrated beneath the crawler and deployed solely by cable tension, eliminating the need for external actuators. Its silicone and foam layers allow it to conform to curved or corroded hulls, while the cable routing is designed to avoid entanglement or damage. Routine maintenance is simplified to cable replacement, magnet inspection, and battery charging, enabling rapid turnaround between operations.

Overall, the design emphasizes portability, fast setup, and safety under emergency conditions. By combining mechanical resilience with direct human oversight, the system provides a practical and field-validated solution for oil spill containment during the critical early hours following a maritime incident.

5. Field Deployment and Experimental Setup

To validate the effectiveness and operational feasibility of the crawler-based sealing system under realistic conditions, a series of field trials were conducted in both controlled and semi-realistic environments. These trials were categorized into land-based and offshore testbeds, each designed to simulate different aspects of an actual oil spill scenario caused by a hull breach.

Land-based experiments allowed for detailed observation and tuning of key mechanical functions such as adhesion, deployment, and sealing performance in a reproducible setting. Offshore tests, on the other hand, were carried out aboard response vessels and involved actual seawater exposure, vessel motions, and the constraints of confined deck operations. In both settings, a purpose-built steel hull mock-up was used, incorporating through-holes and curved surfaces to emulate damage conditions encountered during real marine incidents.

The test campaign focused on evaluating the crawler's adhesion stability on inclined and inverted surfaces, the reliability of the sealing mechanism under different deployment angles, and the overall speed and safety of operation. Insights gained from these trials were used to finalize the system's mechanical design and to refine operator procedures for rapid deployment under emergency conditions.

5.1 Land-Based Testbeds

To validate the system's critical functions before committing to sea trials, a structured series of land-based experiments was performed on a full-scale steel testbed that replicates the geometry and surface properties of a commercial ship hull. The rig consists of a 4 m × 5 m vertical steel wall secured to a reinforced frame and connected to a gravity-fed water tank capable of generating hydrostatic pressures up to 75 kPa. Interchangeable breach modules (Ø 300–1 000 mm) are bolted into the wall, allowing leakage size to be varied without dismantling the structure. Operator safety is ensured by fall-arrest rails, additional stiffeners and a relief valve that vents excess water whenever the internal pressure exceeds 75 kPa. Key specifications are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Technical specifications of the land-based testbed.

Item	Specification
Overall Size	5,730 (W) × 5,600 (L) × 8,000 (H) mm
Water Pressure	Gravity-based hydrostatic pressure (up to 75 kPa)
Water Tank Support	Reinforced steel frame
Crawler Driving Surface	4,000 × 5,000 mm
Hull Plate Thickness	10 mm
Breach Configurations	Interchangeable (300 – 1,000 mm diameter)
Safety Features	Fall arrest rails, structural reinforcement, custom-built relief valve for overpressure protection

Three sequential test phases addressed the crawler's principal operating tasks:

- Phase 1 – Magnetic locomotion on a painted surface. The crawler ascended and descended the anti-corrosion-coated wall repeatedly to verify adhesion and traction. No slippage was observed, even during abrupt directional changes.

- Phase 2 – Contaminated-surface test. The wall was coated with a water–cooking-oil mixture to mimic fouled hulls. Despite the reduced friction, the crawler maintained stable adhesion and completed multiple travel cycles without detachment, confirming the effectiveness of the magnet–rubber interface under low-friction conditions.
- Phase 3 – Pressurised breach sealing. A 500 mm circular breach was pressurised to 40–50 kPa (75 kPa for upper-limit runs). The crawler approached the opening, inserted the mechanical anchor and tensioned the sealing pad via its onboard winch. All cycles suppressed water flow completely, confirming sealing integrity and anchor robustness.

These land trials demonstrated dependable subsystem performance and yielded data for refining the crawler’s centre-of-mass placement, anchor bracing dynamics and pad deformation behaviour. The verified results provided a solid foundation for the full-scale offshore tests described in Section 5.2.

Figure 10. Comparison of experimental testbeds. (Left) Land-based steel-frame setup designed for testing vertical surface mobility and breach sealing. (Right) Floating barge-type offshore testbed employed for full-scale field validation.

5.2 Offshore Testbeds

Building on the validated results from land-based experiments, a full-scale offshore testbed was developed to evaluate the sealing system’s operability under realistic marine conditions. The primary objective was to reproduce the constraints typically encountered during an actual shipboard hull breach—such as wave-induced motion, limited visibility, and dynamic platform

behavior—and to assess the mechanical robustness and deployment feasibility of the system in these scenarios.

Unlike the land-based setup, which included submerged leakage conditions, the offshore testbed was designed to simulate only surface-level breaches. This decision reflected the practical limitations of floating test platforms and was supported by prior studies (Tavakoli et al., 2011), which demonstrated that oil leakage from underwater breaches tends to be naturally suppressed due to buoyancy effects and pressure gradients. In contrast, surface-level oil spills propagate rapidly and pose a more immediate environmental hazard, thus justifying the test focus on above-water sealing operations.

The offshore testbed consisted of a floating platform constructed by interlinking four steel-reinforced shipping containers. Vertical steel panels were mounted on the sidewalls to replicate a ship’s hull surface, and several breach modules were embedded to allow variation in leakage geometry. A 5 m high internal head tank was installed within the container structure, and two high-capacity seawater pumps were used to inject water into the system, generating hydrostatic pressures up to 75 kPa. This arrangement ensured that realistic pressure levels could be achieved while maintaining the structural stability of the floating platform.

Each test followed a structured operational protocol that included a pre-deployment checklist, environmental condition logging, and coordinated communication between the support vessel crew and the crawler operator. The crawler was lifted by crane and placed onto the vertical hull panel, from where it was remotely navigated to the target breach. Based on real-time video feedback, the operator inserted the mechanical anchor and applied the sealing pad by actuating the onboard winch. Throughout the process, system telemetry, cable tension, and pad engagement were monitored and logged.

The specifications of the floating testbed are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Specifications of the offshore floating testbed.

Item	Specification
Platform Type	Floating testbed assembled from four interlinked shipping containers
Surface Configuration	Reinforced steel panels along upper and lateral surfaces
Pressure Simulation	Pressurization via seawater intake and forced discharge through breach ports
Breach configuration	Interchangeable breach modules (300–1,000 mm diameter)
Platform Features	Observation deck, safety handrails, large-diameter piping network

5.3 Deployment Procedure

The deployment procedure of the crawler system follows a structured and operator-guided workflow designed for rapid execution in both land-based and offshore environments. This process was developed to minimize setup time, ensure operator safety, and deliver reliable sealing performance even under adverse conditions such as wave motion, limited visibility, and pressurized leakage.

Each deployment began with the crawler being suspended by a crane or hoist and positioned near the breach site. While maintaining camera alignment, the operator remotely guided the crawler onto the vertical steel surface using its magnetic tracks. Once contact was confirmed and traction stabilized, the crawler was navigated laterally or vertically to align with the breach opening.

The sealing operation proceeded in three main steps: (1) anchor insertion, (2) pad tensioning, and (3) crawler detachment. The mechanical anchor was inserted into the breach opening using a compact deployment arm with three degrees of freedom, allowing precise adjustment even when visibility was reduced. Upon anchor engagement, a tensioned steel cable was retracted by the onboard winch, compressing the deformable sealing pad against the hull. Once sufficient sealing pressure was achieved, the cable was locked in place, and the crawler disengaged from the surface for recovery.

This deployment sequence was validated in both land-based and offshore trials using the same procedure. Figure 11 illustrates a representative sealing cycle on a land-based testbed with an internal pressure of 75 kPa. The crawler approaches the high-pressure outflow, engages the breach with the anchor, tensions the pad, and detaches after confirming full contact.

Figure 11. Field deployment sequence of the crawler-based sealing system. Crawler approaches high-pressure breach; anchor is inserted into the opening; sealing pad is tensioned using onboard winch; crawler detaches, leaving the pad affixed under pressure.

This structured procedure ensured consistent sealing performance, minimal human exposure, and high repeatability. Although manual operator input was necessary for visual confirmation and final adjustments, the system architecture was designed to support this operational model, reflecting the pragmatic needs of maritime emergency responders.

6. Results and Discussion

The series of land-based and offshore experiments presented in this study demonstrate the feasibility of using a crawler-based sealing system for emergency response in maritime hull breach scenarios. Across a wide range of test conditions—including contaminated surfaces, varying breach sizes, and dynamic sea states—the system consistently achieved stable adhesion, reliable anchor engagement, and effective sealing performance.

One of the notable strengths of the system is its ability to operate on vertical steel surfaces while resisting both gravitational and environmental disturbances. The Halbach-array magnetic tracks enabled stable mobility, even under surface contamination and platform heave. Anchor engagement and winch-driven sealing were executed successfully in the majority of offshore trials, highlighting the robustness of the mechanical subsystems.

Operational metrics such as deployment time and repeatability also support the system's practical viability. Although precise timing data and long-term fatigue analysis were not available, the system exhibited consistent behavior across repeated trials. The ability to complete sealing

procedures within 20 minutes under both calm and wave-affected conditions suggests strong potential for field deployment in real-world emergency scenarios.

In contrast to the controlled conditions of land-based trials, the offshore environment introduced multiple sources of disturbance that affected anchor alignment—such as wave-induced motion, platform instability, and spray interference. These dynamic conditions made it difficult for operators to maintain precise positioning, and in several trials, visibility degradation or lateral sway led to suboptimal anchor insertion. This, in turn, reduced the contact area between the sealing pad and the hull surface, sometimes resulting in minor leakage or inadequate sealing force.

To assist with alignment, the anchor deployment mechanism incorporated a drag force sensor designed to suggest the optimal insertion direction based on internal pressure gradients. However, both laboratory and offshore experiences revealed that this sensor-based guidance alone was insufficient to ensure reliable placement. These issues became more pronounced in offshore settings, where the unsteady flow patterns near the breach further degraded the predictive accuracy of the sensor. As a result, operators routinely relied on real-time visual feedback from onboard cameras to finalize the insertion point. While the sensor data served as a helpful reference, successful deployment under real-sea conditions ultimately depended on human judgment.

Repeatability was informally verified through multiple back-to-back deployments by different operators. While individual styles varied slightly, all trials followed the same operational sequence without the need for recalibration or mechanical adjustment. Apparent alignment consistency and sealing success were maintained throughout, though precise spatial deviations were not quantitatively recorded.

No visible signs of mechanical fatigue or performance degradation were observed over the course of the trials. Magnetic adhesion remained robust, anchor insertion mechanisms operated reliably, and operator control did not exhibit any decline in responsiveness. However, in the absence of long-term endurance testing, no conclusions can yet be drawn regarding the system's sustained performance over extended operational periods or storage durations.

Representative scenes from full-scale sealing tests are shown in Figure 12. The left image captures the crawler suppressing water discharge from a vertical breach inside a reinforced steel tank during land-based trials. The right image shows remote sealing being performed on a floating offshore barge under real-sea conditions with active wave motion.

Figure 12. Full-scale sealing tests on land-based and offshore testbeds. (Left) Water discharge from a vertical breach is suppressed by the crawler system inside a reinforced steel tank during land-based trials. (Right) The crawler performs remote sealing on a floating offshore barge under real-sea conditions with active wave motion.

Table 3 provides a summary of four offshore trial sessions conducted at two different locations, Pohang and Yeosu, with varying breach sizes and sea states. The trials revealed that most failures were due to anchor misalignment or reduced camera visibility under fog or spray. Notably, all tests on November 2nd, 2018 achieved complete sealing, suggesting that the redesigned track shoe improved traction and alignment.

Table 3. Summary of offshore sealing trials and environmental conditions.

Date	Location	Sea State	Breach Size	Trails	Successes	Remarks
2018-11-01	Pohang	3	300 mm	4	3	Minor crawler detachment observed
2018-11-02	Pohang	2	300 mm	3	3	Improved track performance after shoe redesign
2019-11-13	Yeosu	3	500 mm	5	4	Anchor misalignment in one trial
2019-11-14	Yeosu	3	500 mm	4	3	Fogging of onboard camera affected visibility

While the technical outcomes are promising, it is important to emphasize the logistical and operational challenges inherent in offshore field testing. Each sea trial required weeks of preparation, including coordination of support vessels, safety personnel, and rental of heavy equipment such as cranes and large-capacity generators. Trial schedules were highly sensitive to weather and sea conditions, often requiring last-minute adjustments or cancellations. In practice, several scheduled offshore experiments had to be postponed or canceled entirely due to sudden weather changes, including high winds and rough sea states. The logistical complexity and high cost of mobilizing large-scale equipment—such as offshore barges, cranes, power generators, and safety boats—posed significant barriers to executing a large number of repeated trials. Moreover, ensuring the safety of the operating crew on the constantly heaving testbed platform further limited the duration and frequency of tests. These challenges directly constrained the amount of experimental data that could be collected during the project.

Furthermore, several offshore experiments were conducted in the presence of official observers from the Korea Coast Guard, whose operational feedback influenced test protocols. The selection of test sites was also carried out with direct support from the Coast Guard, who assisted in identifying safe yet realistic maritime locations. These aspects underscore the real-world complexity of implementing such systems and the institutional collaboration required for successful development and validation.

Despite these constraints, the system demonstrated reliable sealing performance under varied conditions. Future improvements—such as semi-automated alignment aids, enhanced visual feedback, and mechanisms for confirming successful anchor insertion—will further strengthen its utility. Extended testing under corrosive and long-duration conditions is also necessary to validate long-term reliability.

Although the technology proved functional under field conditions, its advancement toward commercialization encountered additional challenges. Following the project's conclusion, further government-funded development was not pursued, and technology transfer was proposed as the next step. However, potential industry partners expressed concerns about the limited domestic demand—primarily restricted to a single public agency—and the difficulty of international market entry for a system still in an early validation stage. These factors illustrate the broader obstacles that often exist between prototype demonstration and practical adoption, especially for specialized emergency response technologies in niche maritime applications.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

This study presented the design, implementation, and full-scale evaluation of a crawler-based sealing system for rapid mitigation of ship-hull breaches under emergency maritime conditions. Land-based and offshore experiments confirmed the platform's ability to adhere to vertical steel

surfaces, insert a mechanical anchor, and apply sealing force reliably in both calm and wave-affected seas. Sealing operations succeeded across multiple breach diameters and contamination scenarios, and deployment times were consistently held below 20 minutes, validating the system's suitability for real-world spill response where early intervention is critical. Field trials, conducted with logistical support and oversight from the Korea Coast Guard, underscored the technology's practicality beyond controlled laboratory settings by accounting for equipment rental, weather uncertainty, and stringent safety requirements.

Although the core prototype has not yet entered mass production, the project has already generated tangible downstream impacts. Two industrial partners have secured follow-up government grants to develop magnetic-crawler platforms for nondestructive inspection of large steel structures, directly extending the Halbach-array track technology proven here. A third company refined the project's anchor into a stand-alone, pad-less sealing device that has been adopted by the Republic of Korea Navy and honored as an outstanding national defense innovation. These derivative successes demonstrate that, even as the original system continues to mature, its constituent technologies are catalyzing commercially viable solutions in adjacent domains.

Building on these results, future development should concentrate on automated alignment aids that mitigate wave-induced misalignment, more robust visual feedback systems for fog or spray conditions, and extended corrosion-endurance testing to qualify the system for multi-year service life. Efforts to reduce weight and modularize components would broaden applicability to confined structures such as offshore wind monopiles and storage tanks while lowering logistical barriers.

In summary, the crawler-based sealing system offers a credible path toward field-ready, remotely operated hull-breach mitigation. Its demonstrated performance under realistic conditions, combined with the emergence of derivative commercial products, signals a meaningful step forward for maritime safety and environmental protection. Continued technical refinement, coupled with institutional and industrial collaboration, will be essential to convert the prototype into a fully operational product and to expand its impact across the wider marine sector.

Acknowledgment

This research was supported by the Korea Coast Guard through the national R&D project titled "Development of an Externally Deployable Hull Breach Sealing System for Emergency Marine Oil Spill Response" (Project No. 1535000085). The project was carried out at the Korea Institute of Robotics and Technology Convergence (KIRO) from May 2016 to December 2019. The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial and technical support provided under this program.

Funding: This work was supported by the Korea Institute of Marine Science and Technology Promotion (KIMST) [grant number 1535000085], funded by the Korea Coast Guard, Republic of Korea.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (by OpenAI) to improve the clarity and readability of the English text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Supplementary Material

- Video 1. Offshore full-scale sealing test (Figure 12).
- Video 2. Land-based sealing test with vertical hull plate (Figure 11).
- Video 3. Early land-based trial showing anchor mechanism.
- Video 4. Assembly and stabilization of the offshore platform.
- Video 5. Land-based sealing test conducted with a submerged breach surface located inside an overhead tank.

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